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Student Registration and Records Management Services of the Three Private Universities in the Philippines: Basis for Academic Records Digitization

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the extent of implementation of the Student Registration and Records Management Services as basis for student Academic Record Digitization among three (3) private schools in the Global South. Utilizing descriptive-evaluative study, the simple random sampled respondents evaluated the services of the SRMMO with a researcher-made questionnaire validated through content validity. Analyzed through frequency and percentage distribution, weighted mean, Kruskal Wallis Test for significant difference, Fisher's Exact Test and Kendall tau_b for significant relationship, results revealed that the majority of the respondents moderately felt the problems encountered with the SRRMO services specifically on lack of admission requirements and non-observance of enrolment schedule. The researcher recommends therefore that a more accessible and convenient enrolment scheme be implemented among schools. Hence, Digitization of students' registration and records shall be instituted.

INTRODUCTION

The main objective of the Records Management Office is to provide an institution with a service that enables staff to establish and maintain a framework of uniform recordkeeping application and practices, effective retention and disposal processes and the efficient process of storing and retrieving records. Services include management of school records, legal agreements, consultancy, training, education and archiving (Kasumba, 2013).

Private Schools- Student Registration and Record Management Office (SRRMO) records are the school's memory, and such are vital asset for on-going operations, providing valuable evidence of activities and transactions carried out by the organization. It documents the actions, transactions and serves as a reliable and accurate evidence of the decisions made by the authority. Being a private organization, SRRMO receives a substantial evaluation from various accrediting bodies. Given this, fulfilment of the principles of accountability and transparency is particularly important (Purcia & Merida, 2021).

Records management is one of the crucial facets of institutional progress. Any academic institution shall put forth efforts in attaining a centralized record management system that would respond to the various needs of the school's clientele from enrolment to release of academic documents that provide salient information about the learners enrolled (Manikas, 2015).

A number of problems however are associated with student academic record management include improper course registration, late release of students' results, inaccuracy due to manual and tedious calculation and retrieval difficulties/inefficiency (Lewellen, 2015). In most cases the data generated by academic institutions are usually created in non-delineated files for use by different departments/units within the institutions with

the same data appearing on several of these files (Purcia, et.al., 2021). This means that a simple change of address would have to be processed in two and probably three or four places, depending on the number of other files on which these data appears (Eludire, 2011).

With the considerable number of students from the Basic Education Department to the School of Graduate Studies of the three private schools punching from 4,205 for School Year (SY) 2016-2017; 3,346 for SY 2017-2018; and 3,544 for SY 2018-2019 in college, the increasing number of Senior High School students, and the corresponding number of graduates for three consecutive years with 367 for SY 2016-2017; 377 for SY 2017-2018; and 377 for SY 2018-2019 in college, the increasing graduates from the Basic Education Department year by year, private schools are posed with a challenge on how records management can be made a lot accessible, up-to-date and generative. With the number of students who would opt to seek advice for possible enrolment and/or requests of the release of essential documents for whatever legal purposes these would serve them, it is high time to conduct a study that would respond to these calls (Akor & Udensi, 2014).

Consequently, evaluating the extent of implementation of the SRRMO services was an essential investigation that captured the authentic and genuine sources of information from which the school's clientele perceptions on how effective and efficient its student record management system. Findings of which would be the basis of a proposed Digitization of all student registration and record management in all of these private schools.

Research Questions

This study determined the extent of implementation of Student Registration and Record Management in three (3)

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private schools in the Global South namely, Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College, La Milagrosa Academy and Christ the King College, respectively.

Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 age;
 - 1.2 gender; and
 - 1.3 program enrolled?
2. What is the extent of implementation of the Students Registration and Record Management in terms of:
 - 2.1. Student Records
 - 2.2. Student Admissions
 - 2.3. Student Liaison/External Assistance
 - 2.4. Student Recruitment
 - 2.5. Student Academic Records Release
3. Is there a significant difference on the perceptions of the respondents as regards the extent of implementation of the Students Registration and Record Management when grouped according to their profile ?
4. What are the problems encountered by students in the implementation of the intervention programs?
5. Is there a significant difference on the problems encountered by the respondents when grouped according to their profile ?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the perceptions of the respondents as regards the extent of implementation of the Students Registration and Record Management with the problems encountered by the students as regards implementation of the intervention programs?
7. Is there a significant relationship between the perceptions of the respondents as regards the extent of implementation of the Students Registration and Record Management with the problems encountered by the students as regards implementation of the intervention programs?
8. What enhancement program can be proposed based on the findings of the study?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Records management is a rational and practical approach to the development, maintenance, use, and dispose of records, as well as the information included in those records. An organization can control both the quality and quantity of information it creates when it has a viable records management program in place; it can maintain the information in a way that effectively serves its needs; and it can efficiently dispose of recorded information when it is no longer valuable (Penn et al 1994).

Any organization that wishes to function successfully and continue providing services must maintain some sort of record (Iwhiwu, 2005). As a result, records, in any format, are valuable sources of information and knowledge. Effective records administration, according to Kemoni and Wamukoya (2005), offers information necessary for an organization's proper functioning.

In every institution, records of various types are created in accordance with their role, activity, and transactions.

The goal of a records management system is to capture, maintain, and make documents accessible when they are required. It is vital therefore to note that records management theory and practice both emphasize the importance of developing a records and information framework that adheres to worldwide records management standards. ISO 15489 – 2001, in particular, is a helpful resource. The succeeding themes are discussed as relevant resource in providing context to the current study.

Records serves as basis for good governance. Almost every component of the governance process requires the use of records. The availability and access to information maintained in records determines the efficacy and efficiency of the public service across a wide range of government tasks. Badly maintained records have a negative impact on a wide range of public sector changes, and development programs are frequently difficult to undertake and sustain in the absence of well-controlled records (World Bank, 2000b). Information that is well managed is critical for accountability, which is the bedrock of democratic governance. The preservation of human rights, poverty reduction, rule of law, economic development democratization, and accountability framework should all be based on accurate official records.

According to the World Bank (2000b), there is a link between important governance goals and the records needed to support them, as shown in the diagram below.

Governance Objectives	Key Records Required
Rule of law	Legislative records, court records, police records and prison records
Accountability	Accounting records, procurement records, tax records, customs records, electoral registers, policy files, case files
Management of state resources	Budget papers, policy files, accounting records, personnel records, payroll records, procurement records, fixed assets register, property registers
Protection of entitlement	Pension records, social security records, land registration records, birth and death records
Service of citizens	Hospital records, school records, environmental monitoring records
Foreign relations and international obligations	Treaties, correspondence with national and international bodies, loan agreements

Policy and regulatory framework provides blueprint for records management services. A records management

policy is a written document that is required for the implementation of a records management program. The policy's purpose should be to create and manage authentic, trustworthy, and usable records that can support corporate tasks and activities. The policy should be established and accepted at the highest levels of decision-making, and it should be widely disseminated throughout the organization (ISO 15489:2001, Clause 6). According to findings at these private schools, there is no such policy governing the management of student records. Colleges lack the mandate and direction for the creation, use, and preservation of records in the absence of such a policy. This study backs up the findings of several other studies that show the significant obstacles of implementing an effective legislative and legal framework for keeping data in whatever format (IRMT 2008, Nengomasha 2009, Adams 2010 and Mensah 2013).

In terms of records creation and capturing, the records management services record-keeping responsibilities include generating, collecting, capturing, and receiving records. Scholars of records management theory and practice agree that organizations should, in principle, create and capture records of all activities involving more than one party, as well as identify and record every process that generates records (Shepherd and Yeo 2003, Reed 1997)

The SRO, according to the findings, keeps both academic and administrative records. These documents are maintained in a file constructed of stiff manila that is somewhat larger than the documents filed. The file cover encloses the papers to protect them from damage caused by handling and use. They are pre-printed covers featuring the college's name and other information. Individual documents within a file are secured by a treasury tag, which is formed up of twisted threads.

Information is best captured on an appropriate media once it is created so that it may be easily accessed for institutional assistance. Information is recorded on both paper and electronic media at the college. Paper, on the other hand, is the most common method of recording data. Keakopa (2006) affirmed that records were kept in both paper and electronic versions in all government agencies, with the majority of documents being kept in paper format.

In ensuring proper student records management, a process manual is a document that provides declarations of duties and defines the responsibilities of employees in order to improve efficiency. According to Ellison (2006), the goal of a procedural manual is to assist users in understanding and implementing the records management program's procedures. A procedure manual has three main purposes: training new employees, providing a reference point for employees who have been transferred or allocated new duties, and preventing role duplication. Management methods become extremely challenging in the absence of a procedural manual. The findings found that there is no such manual guiding workers at the polytechnic in the maintenance of student records.

This is further organized using classification and coding schemes. The ability to retrieve records quickly and accurately is primarily determined by how effectively they are organized and classified. As a result, records classification systems should mirror an organization's business activities. According to Shepherd and Yeo (2003), classification schemes are based on an examination of functions, processes, and activities, and they document the structure of a records management system as well as the relationship between records and the activities that generate them. A classification scheme lays forth the principles for assigning a unique identifier to each file or document. This is referred to as coding.

Further, it is essential to preserve records management for appraisal, retention and disposition. Organizations cannot keep files indefinitely, regardless of their format. The use of appraisal tools to support judgments about retention, that is, which records can be destroyed and which records merit longer-term or indefinite retention, is emphasized in records management theory and practice (Shepherd and Yeo 2003)

As a result, effective record management necessitates the establishment of protocols for the timely disposal of records that are no longer required to support ongoing operations. A retention schedule is a control document or policy statement that outlines record categories and the time period for which they should be disposed of or retained.

There are no norms or policies regarding the disposition of student records at these private schools. Students' records are retained for as long as they are enrolled at the college. Their records are transmitted to the "archives" once their programs of study are completed. Unfortunately, due to the lack of a records disposition program, the college has a substantial backlog of noncurrent records.

According to a study done by Balasu (2009), there is no public sector organization in Ghana that uses an agency-specific timetable because they do not exist. The lack of an agency-specific timeline, according to Balasu, is a fundamental flaw in the government's disposition infrastructure. According to the IRMT (2003), the ESARBICA region has no records retention and disposition rules, among other issues.

Similarly, records storage and preservation is critical for records management because it guarantees that records remain safe, intact, and accessible for as long as users require them (Shepherd and Yeo 2003). Records require storage conditions and handling techniques that consider their physical and chemical qualities, according to ISO 15489 – 1 (2001) SECTION 9.6. Current records are maintained on wooden shelves and in metal filing cabinets, with some taking up space on the several colleges and universities in the country. Non-current student records, on the other hand, are housed in a facility labeled "archives."

Lastly, personnel training and development should be given emphasis particularly on records management services and academic digitalization. Organizations

should create continuing records management training programs, according to international records management practice (ISO 15489-1: 2001: Section ii). Organizations might collaborate with external bodies to design or set up this training.

Only few offices at these private schools have proper records management training, according to the findings. It is so impossible to maintain an effective records-keeping system in such a setting. The IRMT (2003) performed studies in the ESARBICA region that revealed a shortage of basic capabilities in handling records and archives. Lack of training, according to Nengomesha (2009), is another factor that contributes to poor record-keeping in Namibia’s public sector. In Ghana, Mensah (2011) and Adams (2010) confirm this tendency, stating that most registry workers in the MMDAs are untrained in record keeping.

METHOD

This study utilized the descriptive-evaluative research method. This study was a descriptive-evaluative research since the result of the study evaluated the perceptions of the respondents as regards the extent of implementation of the Students Registration and Record Management Services as perceived by the randomly-selected respondents. Evaluation research is a research that has an aim to provide information for decision maker (policy maker) related to a power or strength of a program, seen from its effectiveness, cost, device, etc. For instance are the implementations of curriculum, an implementation of contextual learning model, etc (Ary, 1990).

Further, this study involved the randomly-selected students of the three mentioned private schools across colleges and departments. Through simple random sampling, the researchers identified the number of

students who were involved in this study from every college and department. Since all students have engaged with SRRMO services from enrolment to record release, a simple random sampling technique was necessarily undertaken as every student shares the same engagement unit with the services of the office.

As to data analysis, the data gathered were treated using different statistical tools. For the profile of the respondents, simple frequency and percentage distribution was used. For the extent of implementation of the Students Registration and Record Management services, weighted mean was used. On the other hand, for the problems encountered by the students on the implementation of the intervention programs, weighted mean was used. Meanwhile, the significant difference on the perceptions of the respondents as regards the extent of implementation of the Students Registration and Record Management services when grouped according to their profile, Kruskal Wallis Test was used. Then, the significant difference on the problems encountered by the respondents when grouped according to their profile, Kruskal Wallis Test was used. For the significant relationship on the perceptions of the respondents as regards the extent of implementation of the Students Registration and Record Management services when grouped according to their profile, Fisher’s Exact Test for Independence was used. Finally, the significant relationship between the perceptions of the respondents as regards the extent of implementation of the Students Registration and Record Management services and their problems encountered, Kendall Tau-B test for correlation was used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

On the Profile of the Respondents

Table 1: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Profile of the Respondents in terms of Age

Profile of the Respondents in terms of Age		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	18 and below	20	23.3	23.3	23.3
	19 – 25 age	53	61.6	61.6	59.3
	26 – 30 age	10	11.6	11.6	91.9
	31 – 35 age	2	2.3	2.3	97.7
	36 – 40 age	1	1.2	1.2	100.0
	Total	86	100.0	100.0	

After a series of data analysis and treatment, the researchers involved eighty-six (86) total number of respondents in this investigation. Their profile is presented in a tabular form below. Table 1 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of age.

It can be noticed from the table above that there are twenty (20) number students whose ages are below 18, fifty three (53) of them age from 19 to 25 years of age, ten (10) are 26 to 30 years old, two (2) are 31 to 35 years old and only one (1) ages from 36 to 40 years old. It can be implied that majority of the respondents’ age ranges from 19 to 25 which means that they are in the right school age for college degrees enrolled. Meanwhile, table 2 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of gender.

It can be gleaned from the table above that fifty (50) of the respondents are male and thirty-six (36) of them are female. It can be implied that majority of the respondents are males and this can be attributed to the courses enrolled by the respondents who answered the survey questionnaire which are normally dominated by men. Meanwhile, table 3 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of program enrolled.

It can be observed from the table above that majority of the respondents are equally distributed. This is due to the chosen sampling technique (in this case quota sampling). This is because all students share similar amount of engagement with the services of SRRMO giving all students the chance to be part of this probe but

Table 2: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the profile of the respondents in terms of Gender

Profile of the Respondents in terms of Age		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Female	36	41.9	41.9	41.9
	Male	50	58.1	58.1	100.0
	Total	86	100.0	100.0	

Table 3: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Profile of the Respondents in terms of Age

Programs Enrolled		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	ABM	10	11.6	11.6	11.6
	BEED	2	2.3	2.3	14.0
	BSCA	10	11.6	11.6	25.6
	BSCS	3	3.5	3.5	29.1
	BSED	3	3.5	3.5	32.6
	BSMarE	10	11.6	11.6	44.2
	BSMLS	10	11.6	11.6	55.8
	BSMT	10	11.6	11.6	67.4
	BSN	10	11.6	11.6	79.1
	BSRT	8	9.3	9.3	88.4
	STEM	10	11.6	11.6	100.0
	Total	86	100.0	100.0	

specifically identified in number by quota.

On the Extent of Implementation of SRRMO Services
The table below presents the perceptions of the respondents on the extent of implementation of SRRMO services.

Based from the table above, it can be noted that all the Key Result Areas (KRA's of the SRRMO services were perceived to be Implemented. This means that all the services that are within the expected outcomes of the office are perceived to have served the students' needs. Only the Student Recruitment has high implementation. This can be attributed to the organized orientation programs that the school implements before the start of regular classes.

On the Significant Difference of the Perceptions of the Respondents with SRRMO Services

The table below presents the test of significant difference on the perceptions of the respondents on the extent of implementation of SRRMO services when grouped according to their profile. Utilizing Kruskal Wallis test for significant difference, it can be gleaned that with the asymptotic significance value (p-value) of age with 0.759, gender with 0.273, and program enrolled with 0.580, these p-values are greater than the 0.05 accepted margin of error of level of significance, therefore the null hypothesis is accepted that there is no significant difference with the perceptions of the respondents as regards the implementation of the SRRMO services. This further means that regardless of the respondents' age, gender, and programs enrolled, they still perceive the same way as how SRRMO implements their services and in this case, implemented and even highly implemented.

On the Problems Encountered by the Respondents

The table below presents the problems encountered by the respondents as regards the extent of implementation of SRRMO services.

Based from the table above, it can be noted that all the respondents uniformly perceived the same amount of

Moderately Felt problems they encountered with the SRRMO services. This means that there is an amount of problems that students encounter in the services rendered by the SRRMO but these moderately affect them. These are largely the lack of admission requirements and non-observance of the schedule of enrolment. The influx of students during the enrollment process can also be attributory to this finding.

On the Significant Difference of the Perceptions of the Respondents with SRRMO Services

The table below presents the test of significant difference on the perceptions of the respondents on the extent of implementation of SRRMO services when grouped according to their profile.

Utilizing Kruskal Wallis test for significant difference, it can be gleaned that with the asymptotic significance value (p-value) of age with 0.759, gender with 0.273, and program enrolled with 0.580, these p-values are greater than the 0.05 accepted margin of error of level of significance, therefore the null hypothesis is accepted that there is no significant difference with the perceptions of the respondents as regards the implementation of the SRRMO services. This further means that regardless of the respondents' age, gender, and programs enrolled, they still perceive the same way as how SRRMO implements their services and in this case, implemented and even highly implemented.

On the Significant Relationship between the Perceptions of the Respondents with SRRMO Service when grouped according to their Profile

The table below presents the test of significant relationship on the perceptions of the respondents about the extent of implementation of SRRMO services when grouped according to their profile.

The first table below presents the significant relationship on the perceptions of the respondents about the extent of implementation of SRRMO services according to their age.

Table 4: Perceptions of the Respondents on the Extent of Implementation of SRRMO services

Key Results Areas of SRRMO	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
A. Student Record	4.16	Implemented
1. Organizes records properly and diligently.	4.15	Implemented
2. Maintains accurate and complete database of student record.	4.17	Implemented
3. Issues and collates student forms.	4.06	Implemented
4. Updates student's database from submitted and returned enrolment documentation.	4.08	Implemented
5. Inputs all student documents in the database.	4.07	Implemented
B. Student Admission	4.19	Implemented
1. Issues admission forms to students.	4.26	Highly Implemented
2. Assists students in filling out of admission forms.	4.22	Highly Implemented
3. Manages the entire admission processes including data management and development from enrolment to graduation.	4.20	Implemented
4. Consults with the Dean/Head of the department where the student would opt to enroll ensuring the student meets the criteria set by the college for successful applicants.	4.33	Highly Implemented
5. Undertake an annual review of the student admission process.	4.09	Implemented
C. Student Liaison/External Assistance	4.10	Implemented
1. Assists students' needs on external requirements that are to be submitted.	4.14	Implemented
2. Coordinates student room assignment and class schedules.	4.08	Implemented
3. Coordinates with the Deans/Heads as to class scheduling and posting.	4.15	Implemented
4. Coordinates with Deans/Heads on the lacking documents of the students both local and foreign.	4.12	Implemented
5. Assists parents and other stakeholders visiting the SRRMO.	4.00	Implemented
D. Student Recruitment	4.22	Highly Implemented
1. Conducts marketing schemes to invite students to enroll in school.	4.16	Implemented
2. Manages inquiries from prospect students.	4.14	Implemented
3. Coordinates with Deans/Heads to conduct school visits, Open House Day and communication expos.	4.01	Implemented
4. Assists/coordinates with the Deans/Heads on the screening of student documents.	4.14	Implemented
5. Orients students with the polices and regulations of the school/institution.	4.35	Highly Implemented
E. Student Academic Record Release	4.10	Implemented
1. Provides conducive holding area for students requesting their records to be released.	4.17	Implemented
2. Attends to students/stakeholders needs and queries.	4.06	Implemented
3. Provides viable access to students' records when asked.	4.23	Highly Implemented
4. Organizes record releasing process in an orderly manner.	4.31	Highly Implemented
5. Releases students' records on its scheduled release given by the records in-charge.	4.16	Implemented
General Weighted Mean	4.156	Implemented

Legend:

- 4.21 – 5.00 (Highly Implemented-HI)
- 3.41 – 4.20 (Implemented-I)
- 2.61 – 3.40 (Moderately Implemented- MI)
- 1.81 – 2.60 (Slightly Implemented-SI)
- 1.00 – 1.80 (Not Implemented at all- NI)

With the use of Fisher's Exact test for significant relationship, it can be gleaned that with the 2-sided Exact Test significance value (p-value) of age with 0.257 which is greater than the 0.05 accepted margin of error, the null hypothesis is accepted that there is no significant relationship with the perceptions of the respondents as

regards age. This further means that age is not associated with how the SRRMO implements their services as perceived by the respondents.

The next table below presents the significant relationship on the perceptions of the respondents about the extent of implementation of SRRMO services according to their gender.

Using the Fisher's Exact test for significant relationship, it can be gleaned that with the 2-sided Exact Test significance value (p-value) of gender with 0.394 which is greater than the 0.05 accepted margin of error, the null hypothesis is

Table 5: Kruskal Wallis Test for Significant Difference of the Extent of Implementation of SRRMO services when grouped according to their Profile

Kruskall Wallis Test	Age	Gender	Program
Chi-Square	1.176	3.893	1.962
df	3	3	3
Asymp. Sig.	.759	.273	.580

a. Kruskal Wallis Test

b. Grouping Variable: TOTAL

Table 6: Perceptions of the Respondents on their Problems Encountered as regards the Extent of Implementation of SRRMO services

Problems Encountered	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. The student lacks admission requirements.	3.01	Moderately Felt
2. Wrong input of subjects/code units by students.	2.79	Moderately Felt
3. Subjects are not available or open for enrolment.	2.87	Moderately Felt
4. Some students do not observe the scheduled date of enrolment/late enrollees.	3.08	Moderately Felt
5. Some signatories are not around during enrolment.	2.78	Moderately Felt
6. Some released TOR do not have soft copy; re-encoding is needed.	2.77	Moderately Felt
7. Late application of SO due to lack of requirements of completion of grades.	2.74	Moderately Felt
8. Retrieval of old documents	2.73	Moderately Felt
9. Late compliance of incomplete grades	2.80	Moderately Felt
10. Late submission of subject description for subject credited or lack of units credited subjects.	2.81	Moderately Felt
General Weighted Average	2.84	Moderately Felt

Legend:

4.21 – 5.00 (Highly Felt-HF)

3.41 – 4.20 (Felt-F)

2.61 – 3.40 (Moderately Felt- MF)

1.81 – 2.60 (Slightly Felt-SF)

1.00 – 1.80 (Not Felt at all- NF)

accepted that there is no significant relationship with the perceptions of the respondents as regards gender. This further means that gender is not associated with how the SRRMO implements their services as perceived by the respondents.

Table 7: Kruskal Wallis Test for Significant Difference of the Extent of Implementation of SRRMO services when grouped according to their Profile

Kruskall Wallis Test	Age	Gender	Program
Chi-Square	7.507	3.913	5.294
df	4	4	4
Asymp. Sig.	.111	.418	.258

a. Kruskal Wallis Test

b. Grouping Variable: Problems Encountered

Table 8: Fisher's Exact Test for Significant Relationship of the Extent of Implementation of SRRMO services when grouped according to Age Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)	Point Probability
Pearson Chi-Square	42.860 ^a	24	.010	. ^b		
Likelihood Ratio	24.472	24	.435	.230		
Fisher's Exact Test	30.657			.257		
Linear-by-Linear Association	3.597 ^c	1	.058	.061	.035	.003
N of Valid Cases	86					

a. 30 cells (83.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .02.

b. The standardized statistic is -1.896.

The next table below presents the significant relationship on the perceptions of the respondents about the extent of implementation of SRRMO services according to their programs enrolled.

Using the Fisher's Exact test for significant relationship, it can be gleaned that with the 2-sided Exact Test significance value (p-value) of programs enrolled with 0.006 which is less than the 0.05 accepted margin of error, the null hypothesis is rejected and that there is a highly significant relationship with the perceptions of

the respondents as regards programs enrolled by the respondents. This means that programs enrolled by the respondents affect how the SRRMO implements their services. The implementation of the SRRMO services largely depends on the programs offered. This can be attributed to the fact that every college/department has its separate unique process of enrolment other than the institutional enrolment scheme implemented in the private schools.

On the Significant Relationship between the Perceptions

Table 9: Fisher’s Exact Test for Significant Relationship of the Extent of Implementation of SRRMO services when grouped according to Gender Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)	Point Probability
Pearson Chi-Square	4.304 ^a	6	.636	.504		
Likelihood Ratio	4.737	6	.578	.529		
Fisher's Exact Test	7.493			.394		
Linear-by-Linear Association	.766 ^b	1	.381	.349	.143	.022
N of Valid Cases	86					

a. 8 cells (66.7%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .02.

b. The standardized statistic is -.875.

Table 10: Fisher’s Exact Test for Significant Relationship of the Extent of Implementation of SRRMO services when grouped according to Programs Enrolled Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)	Point Probability
Pearson Chi-Square	61.208 ^a	30	.001	. ^b		
Likelihood Ratio	48.246	30	.019	. ^b		
Fisher's Exact Test	41.543			.006		
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.768 ^c	1	.184	.190	.097	.009
N of Valid Cases	86					

a. 36 cells (81.8%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .05.

b. The standardized statistic is -1.330.

Table 11: Kendall tau_b for Significant Relationship of the Extent of Implementation of SRRMO services and Problems Encountered by the Respondents Correlations

		TOTAL	Problems Encountered
Kendall's tau_b	Total	Correlation Coefficient	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.978
		N	86
	Problems Encountered	Correlation Coefficient	.003
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.978
		N	86

of the Respondents with SRRMO Service and their Problems Encountered

The table below presents the test of significant relationship on the perceptions of the respondents about the extent of implementation of SRRMO services and their problems encountered in its implementation.

Using the Kendall’s tau-b test for significant relationship, it can be gleaned that the 2-tailed significance value (p-value) of the perceptions of the respondents on the extent of implementation of the SRRMO services with their problems encountered (p-value, 0.978) which is less than the 0.05 accepted margin of error, the null hypothesis is accepted and that there is no significant relationship with the perceptions of the respondents as regards their problems encountered. This means that the perceptions of the respondents are not in any way affected by their problems encountered. This is because they perceived that the SRRMO services were implemented and only felt moderate problems as regards lack of admission requirements and non-observance of enrolment schedule.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, it is concluded that

majority of the respondents’ age ranges from 19 to 25, males and that all students share similar amount of engagement with the services of SRRMO identified in number by quota. All the Key Result Areas (KRA’s) of the SRRMO services were perceived to be Implemented. As to significant difference of the extent of implementation with the profile, regardless of the respondents’ age, gender, and programs enrolled, they still perceive the same way as how SRRMO implements their services. All the respondents uniformly perceived the same amount of Moderately Felt problems they encountered with the SRRMO services. As to significant difference with the problems encountered by the respondents, regardless of the respondents’ age, gender, and programs enrolled, they still perceive the same way as how SRRMO implements their services. Further, there is no significant relationship with the perceptions of the respondents as regards age. This means that age is not associated with how the SRRMO implements their services as perceived by the respondents. There is likewise no significant relationship with the perceptions of the respondents as regards gender. This further means that gender is not associated with how the SRRMO implements their services as perceived by the respondents. And, there is a high significant

relationship with the perceptions of the respondents as regards programs enrolled by the respondents. The implementation of the SRRMO services largely depends on the programs offered. This can be attributed to the fact that every college/department has its separate unique process of enrolment other than the institutional enrolment scheme implemented in school. Finally, there is no significant relationship with the perceptions of the respondents as regards problems encountered by the respondents. This means that the perceptions of the respondents are not in any way affected by their problems encountered. This is because they perceived that the SRRMO services were implemented and only felt moderate problems as regards lack of admission requirements and non-observance of enrolment schedule.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings of the study, it is recommended therefore that since the majority of the respondents moderately felt the problems encountered with the SRRMO services specifically on lack of admission requirements and non-observance of enrolment schedule, the researcher recommends that a more accessible and convenient enrolment scheme be implemented in school. Digitization of students' registration and records would respond to this call. Institutionalization of the best practices of colleges/departments of the enrolment mechanism may be applied in school as enrolment scheme varies from college to college. Benchmarking is suggestively essential.

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